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Abstract

Library Operating Systems (libOS) are highly efficient because the entire software stack, from the kernel to the application, is compiled, optimized, and linked together. However, in certain scenarios, such as code injection for network packet analysis or adding custom drivers, it is necessary to extend the kernel as needed. The traditional approach of modifying and recompiling the kernel source code can be time-consuming and error-prone.

This paper analyzes the possibility of using WebAssembly (Wasm) to extend an operating system kernel at runtime. Wasm is a portable bytecode format that enables fast execution of language-independent code while prioritizing security and portability. Its type system and bounded memory regions effectively prevent unauthorized data access. A prototype module for analyzing network traffic demonstrates the potential, while performance is determined by using standard benchmarks. The performance of the kernel sandbox proved to be about 20 % slower than running the Wasm code in state-of-the-art runtimes on Linux, which is acceptable for a first proof-of-concept.

CCS Concepts: • **Software and its engineering** → **Operating systems; Virtual machines; Abstraction, modeling and modularity; Interoperability; Reusability;** • **Security and privacy** → Virtualization and security.

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1 Introduction

In the past few years, library operating systems (libOS) (compiled to unikernels) such as Demikernel [48], Unikraft [20], Hermit [21, 22], HermitTux [30], and MirageOS [25] have become more and more popular. With the main goal of executing single applications in an isolated environment with high performance, these are typically implemented as customizable single-tasking operating systems that link all required components into a single bootable binary. A classical separation between user and kernel space is typically missing, which means that every system call is just a function call. Especially for virtualized environments, unikernels are ideal for specialization and promise high throughput, low memory consumption, and short boot times.

However, sometimes it is useful to extend the kernel on demand. One example is code injection to capture Ethernet packets for analysis, monitoring, and debugging of the IP stack, others being custom drivers or extensions to existing kernel functionality that can be loaded in at runtime instead of needing to include them in the initial unikernel image.

The most straightforward solution to this problem, particularly in the context of a libOS, is to add the desired functionality to the kernel source code, then recompile and link the entire image. However, this is not always desirable, since

the turnaround times can be long and mistakes in the code can easily harm the whole system.

Linux and other UNIX-like operating systems support the *Berkeley Packet Filter* (BPF) [26] interface or its successor, eBPF [13], for injecting code into the kernel at runtime. While BPF was originally designed for network filtering, eBPF extends the application scope to kernel tracing, profiling, and other custom metrics. These filter programs are presented as instructions for a virtual machine, which are verified and subsequently interpreted or just-in-time (JIT) compiled into machine code for execution within the kernel. In a multi-user / multi-application OS, the kernel's role is to isolate the applications from each other. A security breach providing kernel privileges to an application puts all applications at risk, making it crucial to prevent this at all costs. However, this thread model of BPF / eBPF only partially fits the circumstances of libOSes. In this context, there is only a single application, which also runs in kernel mode. It is arguably more important to offer a framework with flexible, user-configurable isolation capabilities as safeguards for misuse or mistakes rather than to guard the kernel from the user.

In this paper we explore WebAssembly (Wasm) as an alternative technology for extending a library operating system at runtime. Wasm [18] is a portable bytecode format, originally designed to execute fast and language-independent code in the browser. Its primary objectives are safety, speed, and portability, and the machine-independent byte code format enables fast compilation and execution on any platform. Wasm's type system and bounded memory regions collaborate to prevent programs from accessing or modifying data outside their designated heap. Moreover, by using a sandboxed environment, the library operating system can be protected against misuse.

2 Related Work

Our work shares many of the goals with the commonly known Berkeley Packet Filter (BPF) [26] and its successor, the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) [13]. The BPF is a virtual machine with a custom instruction set that is specifically designed to filter network packets without leaving the kernel, resulting in high performance due to reduced context switches. eBPF extends this approach by providing a more general framework for executing code within the kernel. An eBPF program must be verified by the kernel to guarantee that it runs to completion, does not crash or harm the system, and holds the required capabilities [16]. The verified program is invoked in an event-driven manner, either through interpretation or just-in-time compilation. Since bugs in the verifier might result in arbitrary code execution with kernel privileges, several works have addressed the verification and improvement of this software [17, 34, 46]. A wide range of tooling has evolved around eBPF, e.g., a user

space runtime [38], and an implementation is available for Microsoft Windows [12]. Finally, Misono et al. utilize eBPF for dynamically loading programs into their unikernel during runtime [27]. Our goal is to provide a general extension mechanism to the kernel while keeping the implementation simple and flexible. We find that eBPF is designed for multi-process general-purpose operating systems with strong inter-process isolation requirements. Meanwhile, single-process, single-address-space special-purpose operating systems such as unikernels do not have these requirements that constrain eBPF's flexibility. Thus, we aim to lay the foundation for exploring Wasm as a more flexible alternative to eBPF for scenarios where intra-process isolation is not required.

Wasm is a binary format designed for a fast execution of code in a web browser environment [18] and is nowadays supported in all major current browsers [24]. The usage is, however, not limited to the web, as numerous runtimes and interpreters have been implemented to execute the bytecode in different other contexts as well [4–6, 8–11] (see [49] for an in-depth survey on WebAssembly Runtimes). A survey from the Cloud Native Computing Foundation determined the most common use cases for this technology to be “Web applications”, “Data visualization” and “Internet of things” [29]. However, being designed to be embedded in a host environment [18] also makes it an interesting choice for language-agnostic software extensions and plugins with multiple real-world examples [19, 28, 36].

To judge the security and safety aspects of this technology, two aspects have to be distinguished: *host safety* and *binary safety* [23]. The former is the effectiveness of the runtime to prevent unwanted access to the host system; the latter describes the security of the application inside the sandbox. While a general judgment on host security is not possible, several CVEs¹ illustrate that hardening the runtimes is a critical aspect [1–3]. Extensive research on binary safety exists; for instance, Lehmann et al. showed that numerous common security vulnerabilities, such as stack overflows, also apply to Wasm software [23]. An in-depth review on this topic was performed by Perrone and Romano in [31]. In a unikernel scenario, we can assume that the caller of the Wasm module does not want to attack the kernel, as the caller is running in a virtual machine with full kernel privileges, making an attack on the kernel pointless. However, this implies that the caller must still be cautious about which Wasm code is executed, as vulnerable modules provide another potential security risk to the whole application.

Other projects in the kernel and libOS domain have also utilized Wasm: Unikraft provides a guide on how to execute Wasm on their libOS [45], based on the wazero runtime [43]. Similarly, the Hyperlight project has developed a Wasm runtime for their unikernel-like system [7]. And

¹Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures, a database for IT vulnerabilities

Figure 1. Design of the Hermit Library Operating System

finally, the MEWZ unikernel was specifically designed to execute Wasm in a unikernel [44].

All these approaches focus on running a Wasm module as an application on top of a unikernel. In addition to providing an execution environment, we would like to explore extending the kernel with new features, which are compiled to WASM at runtime, in addition to providing an execution environment.

3 Design

We base our work on the Hermit [22] unikernel project. Being a libOS, this kernel is built as a library that contains the essential operating system functionalities, such as scheduling, memory management, or a network stack. Statically linking this library together with an application results in a binary image that can be booted “bare metal” and is most commonly run in virtual machines (VMs). As VMs provide a high level of isolation, they are the regular deployment mechanism in today’s cloud infrastructure. Often only a single application or microservice is run in such a scenario, making it a perfect candidate for a unikernel.

Hermit is entirely written in Rust with the goal of benefiting from the language’s memory safety guarantees. The Rust language has a notable feature for writing system-level software: the separation of the standard library into OS-independent parts called `core` and `alloc` and the remaining parts that build upon OS features like memory allocations and threading. Code targeting the former is indicated by the `no_std` keyword and is referenced likewise in the remainder of this document, whilst applications targeting the full standard library are usually referred to as `std`. As can be seen in Figure 1, the kernel library itself is only utilizing `no_std`, while the application and any further utility crates can make use of the entire standard library, which includes all OS-dependent parts of the Rust runtime like `thread` and `socket` creation.

Figure 2. The loading process of a WebAssembly module into the kernel

3.1 WebAssembly Runtime

The WebAssembly integration for Hermit is built upon Wasmtime [41], a fast and secure runtime for WebAssembly. Part of that project is the Cranelift [35] compiler backend, a fast code generator used for just-in-time (JIT) compilation of Wasm. Running Wasmtime on Hermit as an application does not require any design changes, but Cranelift cannot be included in the kernel parts of the libOS due to its dependence on the aforementioned `std` parts of Rust. As the runtime works in `no_std` mode, we developed a split approach shown in Figure 2: The code generation based on Cranelift is part of a utility crate that is compiled separately from the kernel and can therefore target `std`. This crate also includes the mathematical library and the compiler built-ins, providing symbols such as `memcpy` to user space. The kernel itself just contains the Wasmtime runtime, which receives the compiled bytecode from the helper crate, creates a sandbox, and can then call a Wasm function within this sandbox. It should be noted that this currently prevents the use of floating-point arithmetic, as Hermit supports it only within the application, not in the kernel. This is, however, not a fundamental restriction and could be resolved in future releases. Whether to achieve this via soft-float emulation or by enabling the use of floating-point registers in the kernel would have to be considered and evaluated concerning the use-case-specific performance impact of either approach.

3.2 Sandbox and Operating System Interface

The realization of the Wasmtime sandbox requires the embedder (the kernel) to provide 13 functions related to memory management, memory protection, and thread-local storage [40]. Conveniently, an example implementation based

```

let mut linker = Linker::new(...);
linker
    .func_wrap("env", "now", || now())
    .unwrap();

```

Figure 3. Implementation of the Wasm function `now`, which provides access to the kernel function of the same name.

on `mmap` and `mprotect` is provided by the project [42], which forms a base for the implementation in Hermit. As our implementation is currently single-threaded only, a common shared pointer to a memory region is used to emulate thread-local storage. Enabling truly parallel multi-threaded Wasm modules would be possible in the future by integrating with the proper thread-local storage system already in place.

Finally, it is required that the WebAssembly is able to interact with the libOS. Wasmtime can provide a host function to the WebAssembly code through the Linker abstraction. A simple example showing such an implementation is given in Figure 3, in which the kernel function `now_micros` is provided to Wasm in the form of the `now` function.

A common interface for Wasm applications to interact with the host is given by the WebAssembly System Interface (WASI) [39]. We implemented a limited subset of the WASI Preview1 interface, focusing on filesystem access and standard streams for `now`. WASI supports a capability-based security model [32], meaning that the access to a directory or file has to be allowed by the runtime systems, granting an unforgeable capability to a process in advance. This allows a more fine-grained access control to the file system than the classical *Access Control List* (ACL) security model, also permitting different permission views on the same resources for multiple Wasm modules.

For this work, we have not yet implemented predefined hooks that users can plug into. The following evaluation is done by adding custom hooks to demonstrate general feasibility.

4 Evaluation

The goal of this paper is to test the feasibility of Wasm for kernel extensions. We evaluate this question by first providing an example application outlining the usability of Wasm and then comparing the raw performance of WebAssembly in the context of a unikernel using a set of micro- and macrobenchmarks.

All benchmarks were performed on a server with one AMD EPYC 9354P 32-core processor and 128 GB RAM. Hyper-threading was disabled in the BIOS, and all Linux CPU vulnerability mitigations were disabled using `mitigations=off`. The host operating system was Ubuntu 24.04 with Linux 6.8.0.

```

static PCAP_FILE: Spinlock<File> = ...;

#[no_mangle]
pub extern "C" fn pcap_writer() {
    let mut packet = vec![0; ETHR_SIZE];

    let mut stdin = std::io::stdin();
    let len = stdin.read(&mut packet)
        .unwrap();

    PcapSink::packet(
        &mut *PCAP_FILE.lock(),
        Instant::ZERO,
        &packet[..len],
    );
}

```

Figure 4. Capturing network traffic using Smoltcp.

Benchmark	Result
Compile a small Wasm module	940 μ s
Instantiate a new sandbox	125 μ s
Call Wasm NOP function from kernel	127 ns
Call native NOP function from kernel	0.26 ns

Table 1. Key performance characteristics of our Wasm sandbox.

4.1 Example Application: Network filtering

To capture the network traffic, Hermit was modified so that every packet would be forwarded as `stdin` to the Wasm module's `pcap_writer` function. A basic implementation of this function is given in Figure 4. This example utilizes the `PcapSink` function from the `Smoltcp` [37] library, illustrating the usage of existing code for the module without further modification. The usage of a `Vec` in the code also shows the use of Rust's standard library in the WebAssembly extension—something that would not be possible in a kernel extension. It is also worth noting that both the caller's and the callee's expected signatures are checked by Wasmtime, preventing cross-module inconsistencies.

4.2 Microbenchmarks

To determine the overhead of calling a Wasm function, we evaluated a NOP function call to measure the latency. This function performs no action other than return, allowing us to measure the pure overhead of the isolation mechanism. To prevent the compiler optimizing out the call to the NOP function, we used `#[inline(never)]` on the function and `black_box` on the return value; we ran the benchmark ~ 30 times and measured the average time the integrated

wasmtime compiler needs to compile the Wasm module. As Table `reftab:kpc` shows, this takes 940 μ s. This overhead is introduced solely by loading the module into the kernel. In addition, a sandbox is initiated, but in comparison to the compile time, this can be considered rather cheap (125 μ s).

After loading the Wasm module, the benchmark calls the NOP function 1000000 times. In comparison to a native function call, a Wasm module’s function call is about 200 times slower. But in general, 127 ns can still be considered a small time for a jump into a sandboxed environment. The integration of WebAssembly support (including the JIT compiler, the runtime, and the Wasm image) increases the size of the smallest possible application from 900 KiB to 11 271 KiB (a 12.5 % increase).

4.3 Macrobenchmarks

To evaluate the runtime performance of code running in our Wasm sandbox, we have measured integer performance and floating-point performance using the *Dhrystone* benchmark and the *NAS Parallel Benchmark Suite* (NPB), respectively. For each benchmark, we measured eleven different scenarios:

1. *Native, GCC*: GCC-compiled benchmark running on the host system.
2. *Linux VM, GCC*: GCC-compiled benchmark running in the Linux VM.
3. *Hermit VM, GCC*: GCC-compiled benchmark running in a Hermit VM.
4. *Native, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running on the host system.
5. *Linux VM, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running in the Linux VM.
6. *Native, Wasmtime, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running on Wasmtime on the host system.
7. *Native, hermit-wasm, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running on hermit-wasm on the host system.
8. *Linux VM, Wasmtime, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running on Wasmtime in the Linux VM.
9. *Linux VM, hermit-wasm, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running on hermit-wasm in the Linux VM.
10. *Hermit VM, hermit-wasm, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running on hermit-wasm in a Hermit VM.
11. *Hermit VM, kernel, Clang*: Clang-compiled benchmark running as Wasm module in the Hermit kernel in a Hermit VM (only for Dhrystone).

We compiled the benchmarks for WASI using the WASI SDK² version 27 (Clang 20), for Hermit using GCC 114, and for Linux using GCC 14 and Clang 20. The Linux VM is based on the Ubuntu 24.04 cloud image. All VMs were run with QEMU 8. All benchmarks were compiled with `-O3`. Each benchmark configuration was measured 30 times.

²<https://github.com/WebAssembly/wasi-sdk>

Figure 5. Dhrystone (integer performance). Higher is better.

4.3.1 Dhrystone. Dhrystone [47] is a traditional, C-based benchmark for measuring integer performance. We took the latest version written in C (version 2.2a)³ and modified the time-measuring functions to use `clock_gettime` for sub-second resolution.

Figure 5 shows our Dhrystone measurements. Interestingly, even though GCC generates slower code on Linux, Hermit runs as fast as Clang-generated Linux code, which is the fastest tested configuration. When comparing these times with the fastest measured Wasm times, we see that Wasm runs about 40 % slower at best for this benchmark. We expect this to be caused by additional runtime checks that are specific to the Wasmtime runtime. Additionally, Wasmtime’s Cranelift compiler is optimized for fast just-in-time compilation at the cost of spending less time on code optimization. On Hermit, the Wasm performance unfortunately takes another hit of about 25 %, which warrants further investigation. Finally, a performance difference is not measurable when the Wasmtime runtime is moved from user space to kernel space, where floating-point operations aren’t allowed.

4.4 NAS Parallel Benchmark Suite (NPB)

The *NAS Parallel Benchmark Suite* (NPB) [14] is a traditional benchmark for evaluating floating-point performance of computer systems. It was originally written in Fortran and aims to exhibit similar computational characteristics to computational fluid dynamics (CFD) applications. The last version with serial programming models (NPB 3.3.1) was written in Fortran and frequently uses *common blocks*. Although LLVM’s Flang compiler can handle common blocks, the Wasm linker *wasm-ld* does not support them, as they are rarely used in modern code. This is why we chose to evaluate a C port of NPB, SNU-NPB 2019 [15, 33], which does not use common blocks.

³<https://homepages.cwi.nl/~steven/dry.c>

(a) SNU-NPB EP

(b) SNU-NPB MG

(c) SNU-NPB CG

(d) SNU-NPB FT

(e) SNU-NPB IS

(f) SNU-NPB SP

Figure 6. SNU-NPB benchmark results. Higher is better.

Figure 7. SNU-NPB BT

SNU-NPB contains eight benchmarks:

1. *EP* (Figure 6a): an *embarrassingly parallel* compute kernel generating pairs of Gaussian random deviates
2. *MG* (Figure 6b): a *multigrid* calculation
3. *CG* (Figure 6c): applying the *conjugate gradient* to a matrix
4. *FT* (Figure 6d): solving a differential equation using the *Fourier transform*
5. *IS* (Figure 6e): *integer sort*
6. *LU* (N/A): performing a *lower-upper* (LU) decomposition of a matrix
7. *SP* (Figure 6f): solving systems of *scalar, pentadiagonal* equations
8. *BT* (Figure 7): solving systems of *block tridiagonal* equations

Apart from LU, which would not run on Wasmtime due to memory faults, all SNU-NPB benchmarks were used for evaluating Hermit’s Wasm performance. The results can be summarized as follows: In all benchmarks, Clang generates faster Linux code than GCC. The GCC-generated native Hermit code varies a lot in performance: In MG, CG, and IS, it outperforms the GCC-generated native Linux code; in SP and BT, it performs on the same niveau as the GCC-generated native Linux code; in EP and FT, it heavily underperforms. Except in BT, Clang-generated Wasm code runs quite a bit slower than GCC-generated Linux code, which is expected due to the aforementioned Wasmtime runtime checks and the not-as-optimizing-as-LLVM Cranelift code generator. In the case of BT, the Clang-generated Wasm code interestingly runs faster than the GCC-generated Linux code (but still slower than the Clang-generated Linux code), which implies Cranelift and Wasmtime don’t have much of an impact in this benchmark compared to the optimizing Clang compiler. In all benchmarks, Wasmtime and hermit-wasm performed similarly when run natively or in the Linux VM. Except for

EP, hermit-wasm code runs a bit slower in a Hermit VM than in the Linux VM, which warrants further investigation.

5 Conclusion

This paper explored using Wasm to extend, rather than just run in, a unikernel. Thanks to Wasm, these kernel extensions run in a sandbox, separate from the kernel, and can be loaded at run time. In comparison to eBPF, Wasm was not purpose-built for running in a kernel, which makes it unsuitable for kernels that require static analysis of extension modules before loading. On the other hand, Wasm is more flexible than eBPF in that more software libraries can be compiled to Wasm than to eBPF due to the use of common OS APIs not being available in eBPF, which makes it very suitable for experimenting and prototyping. To demonstrate this, we integrated a proof-of-concept pcap-exporting packet filter into Hermit’s network stack using existing libraries. In the future, the performance of our sandbox as well as the impact on unikernel-specific features and performance characteristics warrants further investigation. Additionally, more advanced extensions, such as device drivers, could be explored.

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